

Data Traceability for Lifecycle Management

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Abstract.

Purpose – This paper studies the benefits of applying a single lifecycle management approach to improve data traceability. Through digitalization there is an increasing rise of “smarter” products. Hardware and software of **smart products** need to be managed throughout the entire product life cycle, requiring product traceability from product and application lifecycles.

Design/methodology/approach – The Design Science Research approach was applied. Data was collected at a Swiss company with around 16'000 employees worldwide via qualitative interviews (n=10) in an IT integration project with dispersed teams worldwide. The identified requirements were tested in an artefact with business using the tool Polarion.

Findings – The main result of this research shows that **product data traceability** can be improved with one life-cycle management tool, which increases efficiency and improves the transparency of processes and disciplines. Findings from interviews confirmed the following requirements: direction, consistency, effort, completeness, visibility, and clarity.

Business implication – Smart Products are of raising importance for producing companies. However, traditionally ALM (software) and PLM (product/hardware) tools exist with different users and purpose. The study suggests the implementation of an integrated smart product life-cycle management tool due to its identified benefits to **increase efficiency** through training of users as well through **harmonization** and **standardization**.

Originality/ Value – The study revealed various perspectives of senior manager and application manager on lifecycle management. Different levels of management in the company, as well as their skills, have different opinions on data traceability and data integration benefits.

Type of work – Empirical Paper

Keywords: – Data Traceability, Digitalization of Products, Lifecycle Management, System Integration

1 Introduction

Through digitalization there is an increasing rise of smart products. **Smart Products** are of raising importance for producing companies. Under smart products we understand hardware, software, and the communication with its environment. Hardware and software need to be managed throughout the entire product life cycle requiring product traceability.

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Smart products have three core elements, **physical**, **smart**, and **connectivity** 1. These increase each other's values in loops 2. Smart products' production increase demand to maintain the lifecycle of the product differently than the non-smart product's product lifecycle management. Smart product lifecycle management tool contains a lot of data about the product, which are used increasingly in the strategic decision making of the company.

Table 1 lists abbreviations, definitions, and their respective technology.

Table 1. List of abbreviations and respective technology (own).

Abbreviation	Definition	Technology
ALM	Application Lifecycle Management	Software
HM	Hardware	Hardware
PLM	Product Lifecycle Management	Hardware / Product
SM	Software	Software

By digitalization of business processes product data traceability is of rising importance. Traceability is supported by PLM/ALM tools. To have a digital platform which contains the complete data of a product and data governance, PLM and ALM integration is necessary to be implemented in the product development environment.

This paper is the result of a one-year research process on product digitalization platforms to answer the question how system integration can be applied to integrate ALM and PLM Lifecycle Management Tools.

2 Literature Review

A literature review was conducted on product digitalization platform and traceability with forward and backward searches. Searched keywords include data traceability, ALM, PLM, ALM/PLM integration, product digital representation, smart products, digital transformation, and product development process.

2.1 Key Concepts on Data Traceability and ALM/PLM Integration

A smart product is a highly complex product containing a big amount of data about itself. In today's globalized manufacturing landscape, collecting, managing, retaining, maintaining, and protecting the product's data throughout the life cycle is a substantial challenge for companies 3. **Product Data Traceability** includes topics of traceability, product requirement management, change management and test management. As a general term, traceability is applied to many sectors. In the field of product development, it is about tracing the changes in the product requirement management, change management and test management processes.

ALM/PLM Integration/System Integration describes integrating ALM and PLM as an integration of two systems matter, thus system integration is the overarching concept. Table 2 provides an overview of key terms and their definitions.

Table 2. Overview of key terms (own).

Key term	Definition
Product Data Traceability	<p>Product traceability can be distinguished between internal and external traceability. The focus of “internal traceability refers to the record keeping of a product information within a single production process.” 4.</p> <p>The ability to describe and follow the life of requirement, in both a forwards and backwards direction (from its origins, through its development and specification, to its subsequent deployment and use, and through all periods of on-going refinement and iteration in any of these phases 5.</p> <p>Defined from a requirements engineering perspective as the term traceability was first introduced around 1970s in the area of requirements engineering in software development 5.</p>
Application Lifecycle Management (ALM)	"It indicates the coordination of activities and the management of artefacts (e.g., requirements, source code, test cases) during the software product's lifecycle " 6.
Product Lifecycle Management (PLM)	"It is the business activity of managing, in the most effective way, a company's products all the way across their lifecycles ; from the very first idea for a product all the way through until it is retired and disposed of" 7.
ALM/PLM Integration / System Integration	"It is a component of the system engineering process that unifies the product components and the process components into a whole. It ensures that the hardware, software, and human system components will interact to achieve the system purpose or satisfy the customer's need" 8.

Throughout its life cycle PLM handles the physical product (HW) from the idea generation to the retirement phase in the most effective way 7. From the part of the software, the digital product part (SW), ALM processes and tools manages SW creation process by SW engineers 9. In many smart product manufacturing organizations, HW is developed by a product development team, and SW development teams develop SW. All the related activities such as requirements collecting, designing, testing, and production are performed separately by separate teams 10. A framework of product traceability includes several variables, which have been grouped around four pillars of product identification, data to trace, product routing and traceability tools 11, see figure 1.

Fig. 1. Four pillar traceability framework 11; retrieved from 4.

Besides data traceability issues within the geographically distributed product development teams, the complex IT infrastructure of the organization and the complexity of the product itself are presenting challenges to managing the whole product from the SW and HW sides 12.

2.2 Product Data Traceability

The main goal of traceability is to improve the **quality of SW systems** 13. Tracing product data requires a lot of effort to document and maintain 14 and laws and regulation are different in each sector. According to 15 SW developers do not see **clear benefits of traceability** and it only challenge them with great deal of documentation effort. One of the main causes of insufficient traceability are distributed teams working with different tools with **heterogeneous interfaces** 16.

Traceability is one of the main **business benefits ALM/PLM integration** would bring to an organization 9. In other words, tracing back all the development data of the product can be accessible in one place. The SW part of the product development data is stored and managed in ALM system therefore, ALM tools enable the strong traceability in the SW development side 17. In the meanwhile, PLM ensures the traceability of the HW part of the data throughout its lifetime 18. When both HW and SW part of the product's data are managed in the respective tools, through integration the complete data of the product will be available in single platform as ALM/PLM integrated platform. This means information will be exchanged between ALM and PLM but the data itself will always store at their origin 19. By fixing the defects faster and earlier

affects the time for **launching the product in the market** 16. Thereby one of the biggest benefits of **data traceability** in system engineering are detecting the faults in the requirements or source code and fix them in a timely manner 16.

There is an urgency to have a unified harmonized global platform to manage both HW and SW development data and activity tracking. The ideal global harmonized platform should provide minimal disruption and replacement effort and involve departments/teams in the product development/delivery process so they can gain on product delivery time, respond effectively to change and efficient/errorless data sharing/reporting and not only in the organization but also with partners and suppliers in completely digital way 12. Figure 2 illustrates the potential design of how data of ALM and PLM tools can be combined in a unified platform as one true source of product data.

Fig. 2. Digital product data representation through PLM/ALM integration 13.

2.3 Research Gap

Research did not demonstrate developed requirements and apply them throughout an organization 14. Companies are lacking standardized guides, requirements, and realistic approaches 9

based on experience and practice to design ALM/PLM integration in their organizations' different departments 15. According to 16 analysis of both, engineering, and business benefits, such as design of data models, design of different engineering team collaboration, design of key performance indicators (KPI) and its measurement approaches are missing in scholarly articles.

Major research on traceability has been done by specific applications on **food** 10, 17, 18, **software** 10, 13, 19, 20, 21, 22 and **automotive** 23 as well as on **supply chain** 24. Recent research integrates specific technology solutions like **blockchain** 3 from operations and logistics management perspectives for “object-related end-to-end traceability” 25.

Further research is needed for “domains with complex objects, such as ... manufacturing” 25 calling for validation in case studies of specific industries. There is a need for understanding benefits of integrating ALM/PLM from both, business, and engineering perspectives in the context of **production** to enhance findings from Schuitemaker 26.

Research Gap

The detailed benefits of integrating ALM/PLM from both business and engineering perspectives need to be addressed.

Research Question:

How a specific discipline (requirement engineering) of the ALM productivity can be improved via a proper tool and further gain the efficiency of it by integrating it with an PLM tool.

3 Research Method

3.1 Design Science Research

The **Design Science Research** based on 27 is applied as a choice of research design to "enhance human knowledge via the creation of innovative artefacts" 28. The developed artefact prototype is a product digitalization platform in form of an **ALM tool** as a technological solution to an important business need 29 to increase the **product data traceability, efficiency in cost and quality**.

The Design Science Research process model consists of six different steps (see Table 3), namely Awareness of a problem, Suggestion to the problem, Development of an artefact, Evaluation and feedback on the artefact and Conclusion and discussion 30.

Table 3. Six Phases of Design Science Research (own).

Research phase	Research question	Expected outcome
Awareness	By reducing the number of platforms what are the benefits coming with it?	Identify the issues of non-integrated ALM/PLM tools in literature and business

Suggestion	By reducing the number of platforms what are the benefits coming with it?	Understand the key elements to build an artefact
Development	How can system integration be applied to integrate ALM and PLM tools?	Develop ALM tool as an artefact
Evaluation	How can better data traceability, efficiency, cost, and quality be achieved?	Define where in the product development process can benefit from the artefact
Conclusion	Discussion on how literature and business requirements differ from each other and what it means for product data traceability.	Assess of the differences between literature suggestion and the artefact

3.2 Data Collection

Data was collected at an international Swiss precision instruments and service provider company with around 16'000 employees worldwide. The company provides applications for different sectors such as pharmaceutical, food and beverage, retail, and logistics.

Lifecycle management at the Swiss company is complex, with a Software Development Centre in India, dispersed teams worldwide, and at least 23 tools and five communication channels, demanding high management costs and bring quality risks. Nevertheless, there is an urgency to have a unified harmonized global platform to manage both HW and SW development data and activity tracking.

Expert interviews (n=10) within the company were conducted within dispersed ALM/PLM integration projects of mechatronic products with members from Switzerland, Austria, and India. This included meeting with the requirement engineering team as well as users. There were two different roles:

User level stakeholders (n=6): requirements engineer, project managers/team lead

Senior level stakeholders (n=4): head of R&D, head of system integration, head of software development center, head of systems and technology.

3.3 Data Analysis and Artefact Development

Interviews were recorded, transcribed, coded and data regarding requirements analyzed. Inputs from interviews were used to produce an artefact which build upon models from the literature requirements. Artefact development happened in the following phase: Learn digital tool, collect requirements from requirement engineering team, test the requirements, consolidate feedback / clarification meetings, and implement adapted requirements to further develop the artefact.

The developed artefact is based on Polarion tool and its integration to Microsoft TFS platform. It collects market requirements, translates them to software requirements, documents, gets feedback, and receives approval via the Polarion tool and then feeds into the TFS platform.

The artefact was selected between alternative options because of its most influential requirement characteristics of backward and forward trace, complete and consistent data traceability as well as visible, accessible, and clear data transparency.

4 Research Outcome on Product Data Traceability

4.1 Requirements and Characteristics of Traceability

The requirement of product data traceability can be described by different characteristics based on literature (see Table 4).

Table 4. Requirement traceability and its characteristics from literature (own).

Requirement	Characteristic	Literature quote and source
Product Data Traceability	Direction (forward and backward)	"The terms forward and backward traceability are commonly used where forward refers forward through time and backward refers to tracing data back to its origin" 26
	Consistency	"Traceability, thanks to the consistency of the data, allows to rebuild the whole history of a product keeping track of all its changes and revisions." 31
	Effort	"Labeling datasets is costly and time consuming so it is important to make them available for use within the company" 32
	Completeness	"There is a lot of traces we can stocked, that is why definition of traceability is an essential step in order to establish a predecessor-successor relationship between one work product and another, Information about each artifact, who has created or updated the artefact, users of the artefact, the source of tasks (telephone calls, documents), formal or informal texts, graphics, audio or video recordings, when was the artifact created or modified, why was the artefact created or updated etc." 19
	Visibility	"In SW engineering related areas, transparency generally refers to a product or process' visibility to stakeholders." 33
	Clarity	"A development process is visible if all of its steps and current status are documented clearly." 34
	Accessibility	"The development process is itself documented, published, and publicized so that important decisions and status are visible to all concerned parties." 35
	Technology	"Today many enterprises use some techniques and technologies to manage data traceability in several domains like RFID, barcodes, ERP,

	etc and in recent years, management SW vendors have added more features to help facilitate traceability." 19
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The requirement of product data traceability with its different characteristics was then evaluated from the business side through interviews. Table 5 lists the characteristics of traceability listed from top to down by decreasing importance (number of times required by business side). The goal of this table is to show which requirement characteristics are the most required to be implemented from business side meaning that it could be the most important requirement for the users.

Table 5: Major characteristics of data traceability of business side (own).

Interview, users Requirements	Characteristic	Keywords	User level stakeholders						Senior level stakeholders				Total	
			I-1 ULS	I-2 ULS	I-3 ULS	I-4 ULS	I-5 ULS	I-6 ULS	I-7 SLS	I-8 SLS	I-9 SLS	I-10 SLS		
Product Data Traceability	Direction	product management activities, e.g. engineering change management, release management, test management	•	•	•	•	•			•	•			7
	Consistency	product quality, company reputation, audit proof process		•		•	•		•				•	5
	Effort	harmonization of HW and SW tools				•		•	•	•			•	5
	Completeness	stakeholders, external partners, cross teams/global teams				•	•	•	•				•	5
	Visibility	transparency of success and error, culture		•		•		•	•				•	5
	Clarity	clear communication between stakeholders				•	•	•	•				•	5
	Accessibility	access by all stakeholders		•	•				•					3
Technology	tools and technologies, technology literacy							•	•				2	

Traceability- Direction

By being able to easily detect errors of the past and intended use for the future can bring cost and time benefits due to having able to faster **product management activities** such as **engineering change management, release management, test management**.

Traceability-Consistency

Having the complete consistent data of a product will result in better **product quality** (less recalling of a defected product, makes it faster to fix in terms of defect detection) better **company reputation** and **audit proof process**.

Traceability-Effort

It is a chance for management to **harmonize both HW and SW tools** to be used in the company by standardizing them and manage by only through central IT service. This act will result in safer **cyber security** throughout the whole organizations especially in **global organizations**.

Traceability-Completeness

Having the complete data of the product enables all the **stakeholders** including **external partners** to be well informed and exchange right data about projects. That would mean better facilitated collaboration between **cross teams/ global teams**.

Traceability-Visibility

Visibility implication applies to the whole organization and management. Transparency of the success and error are both vital in an organizational culture. Therefore, visibility of the **project status** and **forward plan** readily and clearly available could bring a lot of efficiency and ease of daily task handling.

Traceability-Clarity

The whole transparency requirement's all characteristics are implied to management as one. Such as clear, visible, **accessible communication of any data between stakeholders of the project/ process** is the success of the management.

4.2 Comparison of literature and business requirements

In the following section, the comparison of the requirement characteristics is described. Table 6 shows a comparison between literature and business requirements. The presented requirements are listed with their chosen characteristics from interviews. Business requirements are listed with quotes from interviews and implications for management are derived.

Some of the requirement characteristics are matching in certain degrees and some of them are not representing a same goal or meaning. The direct quotes from both requirements are compared, it is possible that when the quotes are in the context.

Traceability-Direction

One of the most unexpected differences in requirement characteristics was on traceability-direction. Literature describes both directions of traceability 26, the business described more tracing backwards in terms of error tracking.

It was surprising that characteristics of accessibility and technology were of less importance to user and senior level stakeholders.

Traceability-Accessibility

Having an accessible platform to **include all the stakeholders** of a project/ process is the base of working together especially in a global organization. **Data, tool, or people** need to connect each other in every stage of an organization.

Traceability-Technology

The right choice of **tools and technologies** to be used in the workplace (**product development and production process**) can save costs.

Table 6. Comparison of literature and business requirements (own).

Characteristic	Literature quote and source	Business quote and source	Comparison of quotes	Implications for management
Direction (forward and backward)	"The terms forward and backward traceability are commonly used where forward refers forward through time and backward refers tracing data back to its origin" (Schuitmaker & Xi, 2020)	"I want to have a proper tool that everyone who works on the requirement of a product development work together simultaneously and have access to the traceability of the different exchanged data is maintained so we know who did what when in case of error correction needed" by Requirement engineer 1	Literature describes the both direction of traceability, the business described more tracing backwards in terms of error tracking. Matching criteria is half met.	By being able to easily detect errors of the past and intended use for the future can bring cost and time benefits due to having able to to faster product management activities such as engineering change management, release management, test management etc
Consistency	"Traceability, thanks to the consistency of the data, allows to rebuild the whole history of a product keeping track of all its changes and revisions" (Corallo et al., 2013)	"When a requirement document is written on MS Word, other stakeholders give feedback as comments on the MS Word document when it is circulated around but those comments are not transferred to MS Azure DevOps when the document is imported. This causes us a loss of the feedback traceability on the requirement." By Project manager 2	Business requirement is more focused on the early stage of product development which is including all the feedbacks and revisions of requirements before they go on to the development phase. While literature describes the whole history of the product through out the lifecycle. Early stage of product development is still a part of product history, therefore the requirements are not fully but partially matching.	Having the complete consistent data of a product will result in better product quality (less recalling of a defected products, makes it faster to fix in terms of defect detection) better company reputation and audit proof process.
Effort	"Labeling datasets is costly and time consuming so it is important to make them available for use within the company" (Anzerchi et al., 2019)	"Because if we get rid of all the middle tools used between different teams to exchange data, it is already saving a lot of time by free up their work load and creates less stress which help the people to be more efficient and effective and happy employees. It is a chance for us to get rid of the old tools which are different in different locations." By Head of Global R&D	Business requirement expresses their need to be more efficient and effective by not working with too many tools which can be replaced by a single tool. Literature mentions that having too many incompatible tools cause extremely labor intense processes. Which shows the both requirements show same meaning.	It is a chance for management to harmonize both HW and SW tools to be used in the company by standardizing them and manage by only through central IT service. This act will result in safer cyber security through out the whole organizations especially in global organizations.
Completeness	"There is a lot of traces we can stocked, that's why definition of traceability is an essential step in order to establish a predecessor-successor relationship between one work product and another, information about each artifact, who has created or updated the artifact, users of the artifact, the source of tasks (telephone calls, documents), formal or informal texts, graphics, audio or video recordings, when was the artifact created or modified, why was the artifact created or updated etc." (Palmaoui et al., 2019)	"We have to have very strong evolved kind of reproduce any of the issues which are coming in from the market even after the development teams or anyone who has done it." by male Head of SWDC in India 1 Literature suggests the many different types of data which needs to be stored in order to have the full traceability. Business requirement exposes their need of having many different type of data storing in order to reproduce the product in case of any issue arises after the product launched in the market.	Literature suggests the many different types of data which needs to be stored in order to have the full traceability. Business requirement exposes their need of having many different type of data storing in order to reproduce the product in case of any issue arises after the product launched in the market. Business requirement states the benefit of having the complete data of the product history which matches the literature requirement explanation of importance of all the necessary data of the product.	Having the complete data of the product enables all the stakeholders including external partners to be well informed and exchange right data about projects. That would mean better facilitated collaboration between cross teams/global teams.
Visibility	"In SW engineering related areas, transparency generally refers to a product or process' visibility to stakeholders." (Bh, 2014)	"I would like to see every projects current used source and how much more resource it would need until the project closes. If I have this information easily accessible it would be easier for me to plan and make decisions for the future projects based on my resource" by Head of Global R&D	In the both requirements they mention about the visibility of the process status to the stakeholders which matches notably.	Visibility implication applies to the whole organization and management. Having visibility through out the business and one's own organization is the base of success. Transparency of the success and error are both vital for the managers to implement in their organizational culture and every day life of the company.
Clarity	"A development process is visible if all of its steps and current status are documented clearly." (Ghani et al., 2003)	"I would like to see each different projects' implementation rate and status" by Head of Global R&D	Both requirements state that the clear and complete documentation is important to have the transparency which benefits business for their future right decision making or being well informed about the project or process.	The whole transparency requirement's all characteristics are implied to management as one. Such as clear, visible, accessible communication of any data between stakeholders of the project/process is the success of the management. This culture, way of work needs to be applied through out the organization.
Accessibility	"The development process is itself documented, published, and publicized so that important decisions and status are visible to all concerned parties." (Bourque et al., 2004)	"The entire portfolio management, let's say if I want to look at all the projects that are active in the retail division I should be able to pull it out from a same dashboard, I can have a project manager view, team lead view and me as a head of the division I can have my own view for all the projects. By Head of SWDC in India	Business requirement explains in the literature requirement what they would like to have in their current process which is to have an access to the process or project position whenever they need to.	Having an accessible platform to include all the stakeholders of a project/process is the base of working together especially in a global organization. If the data, tool or people are not accessible to each other it is a big concern for the management. Therefore having an accessibility in terms of every stage of the organization is management's one of the biggest task to fulfill for their organization.
Technology	"Today many enterprises use some techniques and technologies to manage data traceability in several domains like RFID, barcodes, ERP, etc and in recent years, management SW vendors have added more features to help facilitate traceability." (Palmaoui et al., 2019)	"The reason is, it is a chance for us to get rid of the old tools which are different in different locations. Such as in the USA we use HP Quality Center, in India Jira and in Austria Helix is used." By Head of Global R&D	In the literature, more the mean of data collection from a physical product is described, but in the business requirement more of a product development phase from the SW point of view is described in terms of data collection and management. The matching criteria is not one to one but they have a same goal to collect and manage data.	The right choice of tools and technologies to be used in the workplace (product development and production process) would not only save costs but also result in a better employee retention rate (Rogers, 2020). Because technology literacy and getting chance to grow at the workplace is important for employees in today's technology driven world.

5 Discussion

5.1 Validity of research

To demonstrate the validity of the qualitative research, Shenton 36 requests four criteria to be applied to justify trustworthiness - to be credible, transferable, dependable, and able to confirm. **Credibility** stresses the congruence of the findings with reality. Data was collected through individual interviews of one sub-organization during four months' time as part of a feasibility study on usability. The chosen interview participants were all interested in improving their process efficiency via adoption of a new tool, therefore the data bias is limited. Interviews were video recorded, transcribed and validated.

Transferability demonstrates the possibility of results to be transferred to a wider population 36. Findings are not limited to the Requirements Engineering of the Swiss company. It can be applied in other organizations with SW development processes such as test engineering or change management. In entrepreneurial realities they can scale.

Dependability criteria requires different sections in a study 36 including research design and its implementation, operational details of data gathering as well as a reflective appraisal of the project.

Confirmability demands that the result are of the "experiences and ideas of the informants, rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher" 36. The researcher acted as data gatherer for both, academic sources as well as business requirements. Only in the discussion phase opinion of the researcher discussed the similarities and differences between them. Furthermore, triangulation reduced investigator bias 36 since several parties were involved in the study and the developed artefact.

5.2 Business requirements

Data collected revealed alternative choices orchestrating product lifecycle data. The ideal global harmonized platform should provide minimal disruption and replacement effort and involve departments/teams in the product development/delivery process so they can gain on product delivery time, respond effectively to change and efficient/errorless data sharing/reporting and not only in the organization but also with partners and suppliers in completely digital way 12. In addition, creating a single source of truth for product design related information is a crucial benefit of the harmonized unified platform to manage both HW and SW development data and activity tracking.

5.3 Comparison with related work

In the academic field, several researchers have identified the benefits of **reducing the number of platforms** through different ways such as integration, automation or replacing the old tools. Efficiency decreases through managing different databases of a product 37. Meaning the more

tools are involved in developing and producing a product, there will be more databases, where the data of those tools produced are saved. This does not bring productivity increase but decrease. By reducing separate systems in the production productivity increases are expected. Yang et al. 38 analyzed the importance of stakeholders in relation to use of a new technology. When project stakeholders' use technology effectively, project result is positive 37. The technology efficiency is measure by automation and integration of the existing technologies in an organization. Our research also identified the importance of training for new technology of an integrated ALM tool.

From the practical point of view, several interviewees expressed their wish to decrease the number of platforms and tools, they are currently using by replacing them with a powerful and useful tool. The most efficiency they will gain are reduce the cost of licenses of different tools, proper data management in a single source rather than many different tools' database management as well as project collaboration increase in the project management.

5.4 Other observations

The development of a mechatronic product (smart product) journey requires different disciplines of systems engineering where contains HW and SW part of the product. The cross-domain engineering involves different methods, tools, and strategies to keep the smooth processes and efficiency and effectivity 9.

The study revealed various perspectives of senior manager and application manager on lifecycle management. Different levels of management in the company, as well as their functions and skills, have different perspectives on data traceability and data integration benefits.

Different level of management with different perspectives on traceability

From the business side interviews were conducted with people with **different roles** in the organization. The roles are divided into two levels:

- **User level stakeholders** are requirements engineer, team lead of requirements engineering team, project manager, project team lead.
- **Senior level stakeholders** are head of global research and development, senior manager of systems and technologies, head of integration and verification competence center, and head of SW development center.

Depending on their roles, the business requirements and their implications for their traceability need are different. Such as the requirements engineers have a very specific technical and functional requirements for the tool, whereas senior level stakeholders specify their wishes based on mostly on project management support.

Figure 3 shows the different perspectives of the two roles of a user and senior level stakeholder.

Fig. 3. Impact of different roles and functions on requirements (own).

Another specific difference which has been observed was within the **user level stakeholders**. Some of the requirements engineers require very specific functions in the tool which would help them directly on the workflow to minimize or simplify their effort. But their supervisors, requirements engineering team leads were more interested in the overall capability of the potential tool and willing to create a workaround and adjust their workflow/ process as much as they can. Meaning that the team leads were willing to be more flexible towards the new tool nevertheless the firsthand users were more strictly sticking to their current process and showed less flexibility.

Different functions impact how the tool is used

Besides the difference between the roles, another factor that caused a different implication towards the tool was the functions where the roles belong to. For example, a head of integration and verification competence center was very much focused on not to having not too many different vendor tools in their environment to reduce complexity of integrating different tools effort. In contrary, a project manager was specifically focused on a tool which can provide capability of different project stakeholders working simultaneously without losing any data or overview of the project.

Modifications by senior management

Depending on length to be part of the organization senior managers had different approaches regarding traceability and the use of an integrated lifecycle management tool. In one case a senior manager joining recently from a highly regulated background and used the ALM/PLM integration tool before, thereby knowing its organizational benefits. He pushed implementation stronger than some managers who have been working for the company in the last decade and were comfortable with the way they have been working.

In one case a senior manager claimed that they do not have any need to change their current process or tools despite other requirements engineering teams who wish to change into a better set of tools. One explanation is that either the manager is too senior to have the knowledge about his requirements engineering process pain points, or his team members are truly happy with their way of working which would suggest that they have different priorities, different from other similar function teams.

In general, the interviewees' answers towards questions were impacted by their role in the team, function, and unit they belong to, background experience they have prior and their management level in the organization.

6 Conclusion

The research confirmed that by creating a product digitalization platform through integrating PLM and ALM tools better product traceability, cost efficiency and product quality can be achieved. The study developed insights on characteristics of product data traceability of implementing a proper ALM tool as part of a life cycle management tool.

Contribution to research

The main result of the research shows, that there are sufficient improvements on product data traceability by applying one lifecycle management tool allowing transparency of processes and disciplines. This research confirmed benefits of integrating ALM and PLM to meet specific identified requirements from both business and engineering perspectives. This closes an identified lack in the literature 14.

The study's focus on collecting business requirements, analyzing, prioritizing, and communicating the implementations in the tool of choice with the users of Requirements Engineering discipline contributes to close the research gap. However, it covers one, yet very important discipline of many ALM disciplines 39. The findings suggest that traceability enables efficiency when just one tool is applied.

The developed artefact via the Polarion tool modeled the requirements identified in literature and enhanced their understanding. It tested and iterated the design of novel, more integrated systems, and tools.

Management implications

The research has shown that better data traceability can be achieved by

- Allocate resources efficiently by reducing the number of platforms
- Assign human power efficiently
- Make better decisions through transparency of the project status

Overall good feedback was received on the artefact development highlighting integration possibilities with other tools. Based on the findings of the research, there are two sets of implications for management identified to benefit of the tool:

- (1) **Increase efficiency** of tool by training all users (user level and senior level stakeholders). This increased traceability of product data. For example, an auditing process becomes much easier with one tool to access and inspect for regulators. Also, this enhances collaboration between stakeholders across functionalities as well as user and senior levels.
- (2) **Increase harmonization** of the tool in the organization by standardization. During the business interviews the importance of using standardized suggested tools and SWs was mentioned several times. Which means users prefer to choose tools from a company library of ready to use tools instead of searching, testing, and getting approval of the tool themselves from the upper management. There are three main benefits of standardized solution. The first, cross unit projects will have a common tool to use for their projects. Second, integrating to other SW tools within the company become easier and effortless. Lastly, users will not have to spend resource on finding the right tool for their purpose.

Limitations and further research

The limitation of the data collection (n=10) and artefact development is binded to one international company for Swiss precision instruments and services and its unit to test the artefact. Results are the point of view of a specific industry focus and size of company. From the artefact perspective, it only developed the ALM tool of the ALM and PLM integration part.

Further research is needed to study the benefits of integration through integration the ALM tool with the PLM tool in different industries and size of companies. Also, different disciplines of a smart product development process could be considered such as different areas of SW and HW to fully define the efficiency of the integration result.

Also, existing tools and standard are addressed in detail. Both are very important for the design of novel, more integrated systems, and tools. Further research could enhance the analysis of existing tools and standard of an integrated Life-Cycle-Management tool like how Aung et al did for software changes 20. Also, a categorization of the drivers and motivations as incentives of traceability systems to implement could accelerated adoption of change 24. These are based on benefits of traceability as intra-firm challenges as well as technical / system related challenges. This could be combined with specific technology used cases such as blockchain technology providing object-related end-to-end traceability 25.

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References

- 1 Porter, M.E., & Heppelmann, J. E. (2014). How Smart, connected products are transforming competition. Harvard Business Review.
- 2 Gutiérrez, C., Garbajosa, J., Diaz, J., & Yagüe, A. (2013). *Providing a Consensus Definition for the Term "Smart Product."* Retrieved from <http://www.google.com>
- 3 Chen, S., Cai, X., Wang, X., Liu, A., Lu, Q., Xu, X., & Tao, F. (2022). Blockchain applications in PLM towards smart manufacturing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-021-07802-z>/Published
- 4 Schuitemaker, Reuben & Xu, Xun. (2020). Product traceability in manufacturing: A technical review. *Procedia CIRP*. 93. 700-705. [10.1016/j.promfg.2020.04.078](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2020.04.078).
- 5 Gotel, Olly and A. C. W. Finkelstein (1994). "An analysis of the requirements traceability problem." *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Requirements Engineering*: 94-101.
- 6 Kääriäinen, J. (2011). *Towards an Application Lifecycle Management Framework*.
- 7 Stark, J. (2020). *Product Lifecycle Management (PLM)*. 1–33. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-28864-8_1.
- 8 Grady, J.O. (1994). *System Integration* (1st ed.). Boca Raton: CRC Press.
- 9 Deuter, A., & Imort, S. (2020). PLM/ALM integration with the asset administration shell. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 52(2019), 234–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2020.11.040>

- 10 Rizzo, S. (2016). *Improving Product and Software Development by Integrating ALM and PLM*. 11.
- 11 Regattieri, A., Gamberi, M., Manzini, R. (2007). Traceability of food products: General framework and experimental evidence. *Journal of food engineering*, 81, 347–356.
- 12 Keis, A., Denman, S., & Macdonald, D. (2016). *New Approaches to ALM/PLM Cross-Discipline Product Development at Airbus*.
- 13 Spanoudakis, G., & Zisman, A. (2005). Software Traceability: Roadmap. In *Handbook Of Software Engineering And Knowledge Engineering* (pp. 395–428).
https://doi.org/10.1142/9789812775245_0014.
- 14 Ebert, C. (2013). Improving engineering efficiency with PLM/ALM. *Software & Systems Modeling*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10270-013-0347-3>.
- 15 Deuter, A., Otte, A., Ebert, M., & Pospel-Dölken, F. (2018). Developing the Requirements of a PLM/ALM Integration: An Industrial Case Study. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 24, 107–113.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2018.06.020>.
- 16 Deuter, A., & Rizzo, S. (2016). A Critical View on PLM/ALM Convergence in Practice and Research. *Procedia Technology*, 26, 405–412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.protcy.2016.08.052>.
- 17 Haji, MH. (2023) Evaluating the efficacy and drawbacks of traceability technology in the quality assurance of the food supply chain. *Adv Food Prod Process Nutr* 1(1): 001-010. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17352/afppn.000001>
- 18 Karlsen, K. M., Dreyer, B., Olsen, P., & Elvevoll, E. O. (2013). Literature review: Does a common theoretical framework to implement food traceability exist? Elsevier.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2012.12.011>.
- 19 Rahmaoui, O., Souali, K., & Ouzif, M. (2019). *Improving Software Development Process using Data Traceability Management*. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i1.10113>.
- 20 Aung, T., Huan Huo, Sui, Y. (2020). A Literature Review of Automatic Traceability Links Recovery for Software Change Impact Analysis. *28th International Conference on Program Comprehension (ICPC '20)*, October 5–6, 2020, Seoul, Republic of Korea. ACM.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3387904.3389251>.
- 21 Mathieu, D., Kelecom, N. Van, Silverans, S., & Dutré, M. (2020). *A Traceable Development and Testing Methodology for Embedded Software*. 1–25. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334051595>.
- 22 Lyu, Y., Cho, H., Jung, P., & Lee, S. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review of Issue-Based Requirement Traceability. *IEEE Access*, 11, 13334-13348.
- 23 Zamazal, K., & Denger, A. (2020). *Product Lifecycle Management in Automotive Industry*. 1–27.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68847-3_16-1.
- 24 Ghadafi M. Razak, Linda C. Hendry & Mark Stevenson (2023) Supply chain traceability: a review of the benefits and its relationship with supply chain resilience, *Production Planning & Control*, 34:11, 1114-1134, DOI: 10.1080/09537287.2021.1983661
- 25 Dietrich, F. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review of Blockchain-Based Traceability Solutions. In: Herberger, D.; Hübner, M.; Stich, V. (Eds.): *Proceedings of the Conference on Production Systems and Logistics: CPSL 2023*, S. 905-915. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15488/13509>.
- 26 Schuitemaker, R., & Xu, X. (2020). Product traceability in manufacturing: A technical review. *Procedia CIRP*, 93, 700–705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCIR.2020.04.078>.
- 27 Hevner, A. R., March, S. T., Park, J., & Ram, S. (2004). Design science in information systems research. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 28(1), 75–105.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/25148625>.

- 28 von Brocke, J., Hevner, A., & Maedche, A. (2020). *Introduction to Design Science Research*. (November), 1–13. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-46781-4_1.
- 29 Hevner, A., & Chatterjee. (2010). Design Research in Information Systems: Theory and Practice. In *In: Overview of Design Science Research. AIS* (Vol. 22). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-5653-8>.
- 30 Vaishnavi, V., & Kuechler, B. (2004). *Design Science Research in Information Systems*.
- 31 Corallo, A., Latino, M. E., Lazoi, M., Lettera, S., Marra, M., & Verardi, S. (2013). Defining Product Lifecycle Management: A Journey across Features, Definitions, and Concepts. *ISRN Industrial Engineering, 2013*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/170812>.
- 32 Amershi, S., Begel, A., Bird, C., DeLine, R., Gall, H., Kamar, E., ... Zimmermann, T. (2019). Software Engineering for Machine Learning: A Case Study. *2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Practice (ICSE-SEIP)*, 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE-SEIP.2019.00042>.
- 33 Tu, Y.-C. (2014). *Transparency in Software Engineering*.
- 34 Ghezzi, C., Jazayeri, M., & Mandrioli, D. (2003). *Fundamentals of Software Engineering*. 604.
- 35 Bourque, P., Dupius, R., Abran, A., & Moore, J. W. (2004). *Guide to the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge*.
- 36 Shenton, A. K. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. *Education for Information*, Vol. 22, pp. 63–75. <https://doi.org/10.3233/EFI-2004-22201>.
- 37 Ramsaier, M., Holder, K., Zech, A., Stetter, R., Rudolph, S., & Till, M. (2017). Digital representation of product functions in multicopter design. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Engineering Design, ICED, 1(DS87-1)*, 369–378.
- 38 Yang, L.-R., O'Connor, J. T., & Chen, J.-H. (2007). Assessment of automation and integration technology's impacts on project stakeholder success. *Automation in Construction, 16*(6), 725–733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2006.11.005>.
- 39 Daun, M., Grubb, A. M., & Tenbergen, B. (2017). Three Major Instructional Approaches for Requirements Engineering. *Gesellschaft Für Informatik*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.35482/csc.003.2021>.